

Investigating the Impact of Chromium and Titanium in Mechanical and Corrosion Properties of Iron Alloy Coating Materials Deposited via HVOF

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Abstract: The present study focuses on fabrication of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating with varying Cr and Ti content and investigates the impact of Cr and Ti content on mechanical and corrosion properties. Mechanical performance metrics, including adhesion pull-off strength, and corrosion characteristics, were compared. 10 weight percent of chromium was found to enhance the hardness, adhesion pull off strength, and fracture toughness by 22 %, 23 %, and 17 %, respectively. On the other hand, the addition of 10 weight % titanium increased the hardness, adhesion pull off strength and fracture toughness by 59%, 7% and 50% respectively. Considering all the performance factor for the alloying element content up to 10 weight %, it is concluded that titanium appears to be more important than chromium in terms of mechanical properties and Cr appears to be more important in term of corrosion.

Keywords: Chromium, Fe alloy based coating, HVOF, mechanical properties, titanium,

1. Introduction

Mechanical elements are used in maritime environments such as splines, valves, and shafts have functional issues due to corrosion, poor mechanical properties and higher erosion rate. These parameters can compromise a hydraulic system's integrity and operational efficiency. Such compromise can lead to leakage of oil, rushed water into ship or component/ equipment failure⁽¹⁾²⁾. The use of a protective coating can help to solve this issue and provide better performance. A coating method called thermal spraying extends the life of underlying surfaces under extremely corrosive conditions³⁾⁴⁾⁵⁾. For instance, HVOF is a common coating method used to shield components made of metallic substrate materials⁶⁾⁷⁾⁸⁾⁹⁾. Many metallic alloy based coatings such as iron alloy, titanium, chromium, tungsten, boron, nickel etc. deposited via HVOF coating technology are the best appropriate for producing coating with excellent wear and corrosion resistance¹⁰⁾¹¹⁾¹²⁾¹³⁾. However, on the basis of several investigations, Fe alloy coating materials have shown special qualities, including reduced porosity and improved mechanical, chemical, magnetic, and corrosion

characteristics¹⁴⁾¹⁵⁾¹⁶⁾. The importance of several parameters on the performance of Fe coating materials was addressed by Sharma et al.¹⁷⁾. According to Sharma et al.¹⁸⁾, thermal spray coating, such as high velocity oxy fuel coating, enhances the strength, adhesion, compaction, and lower porosity. In several industrial applications where improving surface qualities like hardness, wear resistance, and corrosion resistance is required, HVOF seems to be quite promising. Materials based on Fe alloys based HVOF coatings function well in very corrosive and abrasive conditions. In contrast to WC-CoCr composite coatings without Fe alloy, Xu et al.¹⁹⁾ found that the inclusion of Fe alloy (35 weight percent) reinforced into the WC-CoCr based composite coating, created using HVOF coating methods, suggested superior corrosion resistance and thermal stability. In addition to the presence of iron, chromium is crucial for improving mechanical and corrosion resistance. Chu et al.²⁰⁾ noticed an improvement in corrosion resistance after depositing an amorphous Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating Fe45Cr16Mo18C18B5 on 316 stainless steel. Nonetheless, the hardness of coating materials is influenced by the parameters used in the HVOF coating process²¹⁾. Kim et al.²²⁾ discovered that the

FeCrB surface protective coating atomized by the HVOF technique produced improved mechanical, magnetic, and corrosion characteristics on steel substrates at a cheap cost. According to Bakare et al.²³⁾ investigation into the corrosion characteristics of iron alloy, the corrosion resistance in both 0.5M H₂SO₄ and 3.5% NaCl will be stronger the more amorphous the Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating Fe₄₃Cr₁₆Mo₁₆C₁₅B₁₀. According to Suryanarayan and Inoue²⁴⁾, chromium increases the resilience of iron alloys like stainless steel against corrosion.

It is well accepted that the development of a passive layer or superior corrosion scale on the surface significantly improves a material's resistance to corrosion. Wang et al.²⁵⁾ noted that when the Cr concentration in Fe-Cr alloy steel increased, the oxides in the passive layer, such as Cr₂O₃, maintained a more stable state and the corrosion resistance of Fe-Cr alloy was further enhanced. Xu et al.²⁶⁾ investigated how alloy steel corroded in the presence of CO₂. According to the results, alloys with low Cr concentration underwent spontaneous passivation, and only when the Cr content was greater than or equal to 3% (mass fraction) did the passive film containing Cr(OH)₃ accelerate corrosion. It is widely acknowledged that the first line of defense for materials against corrosion and erosion-corrosion is passive film²⁷⁾²⁸⁾²⁹⁾³⁰⁾. The threshold impact energy, as defined by Sasaki and Burstein³¹⁾, is the smallest kinetic energy needed for the particles in a slurry to break through the passive oxide layer on the alloy surface. Consequently, the formation of a thick passive coating might enhance the material's resistance to erosion and corrosion³²⁾. Although an increase in Cr concentration may improve an alloy's resistance to corrosion, the performance of the alloys during wet milling circumstances is yet unknown. The impact erosion resistance of alloys is somewhat impacted by the change in mechanical characteristics brought on by an increase in Cr concentration. Studying how the Cr concentration affects the erosion-corrosion behavior of alloys in corrosive slurry is therefore quite intriguing.

Conversely, research has indicated that amorphous alloys based on Fe-Cr have also demonstrated high wear resistance³³⁾. Comparably, Gao et al.³⁴⁾ discovered that compressive strength was enhanced by raising the titanium content in the HVOF coating CrFeNiTi_x (x = 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6 molar ratio).

The performances of the coating are significantly influenced by the spraying settings. It has been demonstrated that the HVOF sprayed coating made from precursory particles of a finer size exhibits a denser structure, reduced porosity, and fewer defects, hence enhancing the corrosion and wear resistance of materials³⁵⁾. Comparative investigation of roles of both chromium and titanium on mechanical properties of iron alloy based coating is rarely touched by researchers. Thus, the purpose

of the study was to look into how titanium and chromium affected the mechanical, physical, and corrosion characteristics of steel-based components in a maritime environment.

2. Material selection and Methodology

2.1. Materials and Deposition Techniques

All of the component of coating materials—Iron, Titanium, Chromium, Molybdenum, Silicon, and Carbon—were procured from Mittal Materials in Jaipur as powders with sizes ranging from 50 to 90 μm. The powder mixture were prepared by the uniform mixture machine whose compositions (listed in Table 1) were placed in a graphite crucible and allowed to melt in a gas metal atomizer (Indotherm gas atomizer, Jaipur, India) using the high pressure nitrogen gas atomization method. The metal liquids were allowed to melt for a while at a temperature as high as 1700 K until their composition became uniform. At last, the molten metal was released via a nozzle and sieved into particles between 100 and 150 μm in size. The substrate SS-316L plate was supplied by Narendra Metal, Mumbai, India. Through the use of a high velocity oxygen fuel (HVOF) thermal sprayer (Hippojet 2700, Metallizing Equipment Company Pvt. Ltd. (MEC), Jodhpur, India), the coating powder ingredients (C1–C6) were sprayed onto the stainless steel plate substrate (100 mm 80 mm 3 mm) to a coating thickness of 350 micron. The oxygen flow rate of 250 slpm, the LPG flow rate of 60 slpm, the oxygen pressure of 10 kg/cm², the LPG pressure of 6.5 kg/cm², and the spray distance of 180 mm were the coating process parameters employed for coating deposition.

Table 1: Elemental configuration of Fe alloy based coating material

Sample Designation		Fe (wt. %)	Mo (wt. %)	C (wt. %)	Si (wt. %)	Cr (wt. %)	Ti (wt. %)
Fe-alloy	C1	70	5	15	10	0	0
FeCr10-alloy	C2	60	5	15	10	10	0
FeCr20-alloy	C3	50	5	15	10	20	0
FeTi10-alloy	C4	60	5	15	10	0	10
FeTi20-alloy	C5	50	5	15	10	0	20
FeCr10 Ti10-alloy	C6	50	5	15	10	10	10

2.2. Physical, corrosion and Mechanical Characterization:

2.2.1. Porosity and Corrosion Rate

Image analysis software ImageJ was used to quantify porosity in SEM pictures of the mirror finished surface of cross sectional sample. Ten images of each sample were carefully recorded and analyzed from various sample locations. The final value of porosity was taken as the average of ten samples. Corrosion rate was analyzed by using corrosion tester setup equipped with Gamry software that was Potentiostat–Galvanostat³⁶⁾.

2.2.2. Mechanical characterization

Micro-hardness: The Model NEXUS 4303, INNOVATEST Europe of Vicker's Hardness Tester was used to find the micro-hardness value of samples manufactured through various process parameters load was 100gf for 15 second dwell time by 136° diamond indenter. The calculation of average hardness and the standard deviation were on the basis of average reading of five for each sample.

Adhesion pull off strength: The adhesion or bonding strength of coating and substrate is measured by adhesion pull off strength. For the analysis a cylindrical cross section sample were prepared.

The adhesive pull off strength was assessed in accordance with ASTM C633 in the UTM 40, FAN SERVICES Nasik, India. It displays the degree of adhesion between the substrate and the coating. Epoxy resin was used to bind together two cylindrical samples. The sample had a coating on one end and other end was free for the stud. The samples were subjected to tensile loads, and the samples' tensile adhesion was utilized to calculate the strength needed to separate the coating from the substrate. On average, five measurements were taken for consideration of final value.

Fracture toughness: The coatings' fracture toughness was determined using the Vicker's indentation test. The indent produced on the mirror polished cross sectional surface of the coating was marked with a Vickers indenter. To create the fracture over the coating, a 5 kg weight was applied for 15 second dwell duration. The indenter on the coated sample generated the crack lengths "a" and "c," which were measured using the FESEM micrograph. The indentation technique was used by Silder et al. ³⁷⁾ to determine the coating's fracture toughness using (Eq. (1)) and average of 5 indentation taken as a final value of fracture toughness.

$$Kc=0.079P/a^{(3/2)}\log4.5(a/c) \quad (1)$$

The Kc denotes fracture toughness and P denotes applied load over the indenter to generate crack.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effect of Cr and Ti as alloying element on porosity of coating material:

The porosity of the surface coating decreases as a result of thermal spray coating techniques. Thirumalaikumarasamy et al. ³⁸⁾ determined the ranges for porosity as 0 to 10 μm (Type A) and 10 to 25 μm (Type B). Ctibun et al. ³⁹⁾ suggested that the formation of pores and micro cracks can be due to presence of entrapped air during spraying or shrinkage of splat during solidification. In terms of powder composition or raw materials, the factor affecting porosity are size of ingredient, specific density, powder flowability etc.⁴⁰⁾⁴¹⁾. The porosity and corrosion rate of the Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating material with varying titanium and chromium compositions are displayed in Figure 1. It can be revealed that porosity increased with the increase in number of elemental incorporation. Further, it is evident that for a given weight % of titanium and chromium, greater porosity results from more element incorporation and lower specific density of titanium. This is especially true for the Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating material with titanium. Due to more element present in the alloy C6, it indicated maximum porosity followed by sample with 20 weight % titanium content i.e. C5.

Fig. 1: The impact of titanium and chromium contents on the porosity of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating materials.

Figure 2 (a) and Figure 2 (b) depicted the surface micrograph and its image J processed image of coating C6 respectively. Figure 2(a) indicated a homogenous microstructure with the presence of several distinct phases and unmelted or semi-molten Fe₂Ti particles. The visual representation produced by the visual processing software image J for the porosity measurement was shown in Figure 2(b). FESEM picture was analyzed at 50 magnifications on a mirror-polished sample surface at different places, following ASTM B 276 standard. Pore size on average was noticed. Five random locations were chosen to repeat the experiment, and the average pores was used to calculate the porosity %.

Fig. 2: (a) FESEM image of surface of C6 coating (b) Image processed by Image J

3.2. Impact of alloying elements Cr and Ti on coating material corrosion rate:

The impact of variations in titanium and chromium levels on corrosion rate is shown in Figure 3. It is obvious that the addition of chromium has superior effect on corrosion rate followed by titanium. Chromium formed oxide or hydroxides based passive film on surface. Titanium also indicated better corrosion resistance but less than the chromium. It formed stable, continuous and tightly adhered protective ceramic oxide film on the surface.

Fig. 3: Impact of titanium and chromium concentrations on the rate of corrosion of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy coating

The measurement of corrosion rate is performed using potentiodynamic polarization curve obtained after electrochemical corrosion test of all six specimen. The polarization curve of one sample is depicted in Figure 4. With the aid of the corrosion potential E_{corr} and corrosion current density I_{corr} , the curve was utilised to determine the rate of corrosion.

The corrosion potential and current density were determined to be -0.662 V and 1.72×10^{-6} A/cm², respectively, based on the polarisation curve. Using the data of both potential, the corrosion rate is determined using Eq. (2).

$$Corrosion\ rate = (I_{corr} \times Equivalent\ weight) / density \quad (2)$$

Chromium was added, and this caused a thick and stable chromium oxide passive layer to protect against any

external chemical change. The development of two passivation films, one made of CrO_3 and the other of Cr_2O_3 , was the main cause of the enhanced corrosion resistant behaviour of the Cr-rich Fe-based coating material. Both oxides continuously prevent corrosion on the surface. Therefore, the creation of Cr_2O_3 was essential to creating a thick, all-encompassing layer of passivation that was firmly adhered to the substrate⁽⁴²⁾⁽⁴³⁾⁽⁴⁴⁾.

3.3. Effect of Cr and Ti as alloying element on mechanical properties

Hardness, adhesion pull-off strength, and fracture toughness were used to assess the mechanical properties of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating materials. Figure 5 shows the variation in hardness of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating materials. The hardness of the coating material made of iron alloy was enhanced by the addition of titanium and chromium. The increased hardness was attributed to the fact that chromium forms hard carbide as a medium carbide producing element. The formation of Fe_2Ti or $(Fe,Ti)_5Si_3$ was responsible for the enhancement in hardness caused by the addition of titanium. The finding is in agreement with the literatures presented in Table 2. The hardness was more influenced by titanium as compared to chromium.

Table 2: Comparative performance of developed materials with recent reported material

Sr. No.	Reported Material	Proposed Material
1	TiC+50%NiCr Coating on SS410 Steel Author reported that hardness of developed coating increased ⁴⁵⁾ .	Iron alloy coating materials deposited via HVOF. Hardness of coting materials increased by 23%
2	HVOF-sprayed TiC coating, porosity analysis, and mass loss decreased ⁴⁶⁾ .	Iron alloy coating materials deposited via HVOF, porosity analysis, and mass loss decreased.
3	TiC Coatings on Stainless Steel bond strength, and micro-hardness increased while porosity decreased ⁴⁷⁾ .	Iron alloy coating materials deposited via HVOF, bond strength, and micro-hardness increased while porosity decreased

Figure 6 shows how the adhesion pull-off strength of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating materials varies. Increase in adhesion was attributed to increase in bonding strength at particle interface by material diffusion and decrease in internal stresses.

Figure 7 illustrates how the fracture toughness of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating materials changes. The addition of chromium and titanium improved the material's resistance to fracture. Figure 7 displayed the fracture toughness of

every HVOF-coated iron alloy. The alloy C6, which had 10% titanium and 10% chromium, exhibited the maximum level of fracture toughness, as seen in Figure 7. A cross-sectional scanning electron microscope view of the C6 shattered surface is displayed in Figure 8. Figure 8 showed the intermixing of Cr and Ti particles and more stable and stronger inter-splat regions in coating material. Because it takes more energy to break the hard ceramic particles Fe_2Ti and Cr_2O_3 , the inclusion of chromium and titanium was thought to increase the fracture toughness.

Fig. 4: Potentiodynamic polarisation of coatings based on Fe, Cr, and Ti in 3.5 weight percent NaCl solution

Fig. 5: Impact of Cr and Ti concentration on Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating micro-hardness

Fig. 6: Adhesion pull-off strength of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating materials as influenced by Cr and Ti concentrations

Fig. 7: Impact of Cr and Ti concentration on fracture toughness of Fe-Cr-Ti alloy HVOF coating materials

Fig. 8: Cross-sectional SEM image of fractured surface

4. Conclusion

An evaluation was conducted on the mechanical and corrosion characteristics of six distinct compositions of iron, chromium, and titanium based alloy HVOF coated materials with variable titanium and chromium content sprayed on 316L steel. A 10% weight percentage addition of chromium resulted in a 22%, 23%, and 17% improvement in hardness, adhesion pull off strength, and fracture toughness, respectively. Conversely, adding 10% weight percent titanium improved the material's hardness, adhesion pull-off strength, and fracture toughness by 59%, 7%, and 50%, respectively. Titanium appears to be more important than chromium in terms of hardness, adhesion pull off strength, and corrosion rate. But chromium was more significant than titanium in terms of porosity and resistance to corrosion. Ultimately, the optimal performance in terms of mechanical characteristics and corrosion was suggested by the combination of both alloying components. Therefore, HVOF coating with 10% weight percentage chromium and 10% weight percentage titanium (C6) demonstrated as the most preferred coating material.

Disclosure of Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests in this work, either direct or indirect.

Declaration of Data Accessibility

Since the raw or processed data required to reproduce these findings are currently being utilised in an active inquiry, we are unable to make them publicly available at this time.

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